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Time : The Arrow in Real Plane

The equation for time can be described as a complex equation. Like $t + it$. Where time is like an arrow, as described by Newton, in the real plane of the universe, and time is like a river in the imaginary plane of the universe, as described by Einstein.

Thought Experiment:

If a person is harvesting a crop and he changes the decision to harvest to not harvest after one year, then all the particles of the crop will disappear from $x_{11}, y_{11}, z_{11}, t$ to $x_{22}, y_{22}, z_{22}, t$ in the field, leading to a quantum teleportation disappearing from the body of the person who ate it, but there will be no change in time. The variable t remains constant, like an arrow released from the Big Bang to eternity. Because it is $t + 0i$.

Electrons have an imaginary component. If a writer changes the script of a song in cross time past by mentalism, then there will be a change in the imaginary plane of the universe, which will change the electron state as electrons have an imaginary component and the 50 year old song will appear as a new 50 year old song changing the dreamline of the entire 50 years in the imaginary plane or $0 + it$.

Postulate:

Logic is absolute $t + 0i$

And any kind of Sentiment is absolute $0 + it$

Therefore, anything based on logic, such as an AI-generated image, can never change. A digital image with no real component will change with a change in the imaginary plane of the universe. Let us say, by any kind of cross-time mentalism.

But if an imaginary component gets encrypted with a real component then it becomes a function of the real component and cannot be changed. For example: Data encrypted with positions of sun and moon cannot be changed.

Time never changes in reality and is just like an arrow but might seem to change in dreamlines in any computational system based on electrons. While computational systems based on Gravity and Light doesn't get affected at all as they don't have any imaginary component. Gravity is a bend in the fabric and light is a wave in the fabric of reality.

Ignoring the Imaginary Plane as it is just imaginary

Time is constant like an arrow.